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Overviewing the challenges of Sustainable Development Amidst COVID-19 Pandemic in Nigeria

Garba, Ahmad Muhammad Ph.D.

Email: garbaahmad92@gmail.com & amgarba.edu@buk.edu.com

Tel: 08029429462

Department of Education, Bayero University Kano

Abstract

This paper titled sustainable development in Nigeria amidst covid-19 pandemic: disparity crises to fight or flight. The paper discusses key issues related to the role of the various school taught subjects as means but not an end to sustainable development in Nigeria. The paper operationalizes the concepts of sustainable development and disparity crises. It further explains in detail a reflection on the past, present and mirrors the future trends in relation to the contributions of the various school subjects towards sustainable development in the country. It equally amplifies the militating challenges and factors surrounding the present state of art regarding sustainable development.

Keywords: Sustainable Development, Disparity Crisis, COVID-19.

Introduction

The purpose of this paper is to reiterate on the roles of natural and applied sciences, education, technology, arts, literature and vocational subjects amidst COVID 19 pandemic for sustainable development. This is important because the status of our national development today is alarming and need thoughts that will address issues and challenges surrounding its improvement and sustenance. Equally speaking it embraces multi-faceted areas of interest where each component stands to be unique and independent, but all are interwoven and mutually coexist to support one another. The interrelations and connectivity among Natural and Applied Sciences, Education, technology, Arts, Literature and vocational subjects augment and supplement the key indices for sustainable development in our present world. In essence no single component of the theme among the various subjects can be said to account for sustainable development in the absence of the remaining subjects. However, focusing on sustainable development amidst COVID-19 pandemic is bounded by many issues. Before the pandemic, development in Nigeria was plagued by multi-faceted problems or crisis which severely affects its sustenance and impeded the standard desired. As the crisis continue to metamorphose and keep changing from one form to another, a sudden calamity befell the attainment of development despite the efforts that had been in place through teaching and learning of these subjects in accordance with their respective curriculum contents. The calamity which looked like unending crisis, has taken Nigeria to a fight or plight position.

The point to be expressed here is that, as natural and applied sciences, education, technology, arts, literature and vocational subjects are been taught at various levels of education yet the expected level of development has not been achieved as a result of many factors surrounding the dissemination of the contents of knowledge across the various disciplines, upon which COVID-19 pandemic came and exposed the disparity and weaknesses of the systems in its entirety, thus making various stakeholders to ponder on what to do: to fight the calamity and ignore the existing disparities first or plight the calamity by repressing its consequences and address the existing shortfalls in order to pave the way forward?

There is numerous time bounded and context bounded conferences and researches on impact of covid-19 on sustainable development in relation to the aforementioned disciplines world over. Similarly, numerous conferences and researches on the role of these sciences amidst the pandemic within and outside Nigeria have been and are still been conducted. One may ask – what impact do these efforts have on sustainable development amidst the pandemic which still pervades the world? If there is any serious impact, then the state of development in Nigeria would not have been what it is now or different from what is obtained in the developed nations. My guess then is, the present predicament of development should first of all be clearly understood for immediate redress in order to achieve the desired development in its full manifestation and at the same time to strategize towards minimizing the effects covid-19 might have had on it. Hence, the need for this paper presentation on the topic captioned – overviewing the challenges of sustainable development in Nigeria amidst COVID-19 pandemic (James, 2014; Obasanjo, 2012; Nicolia, 2003)

Therefore, the presentation is based on the following issues: the crisis and state of art before the COVID-19, Natural and applied sciences, education, technology, arts, literature and vocational subjects in the pandemic era and quest for sustainable development strategies. However, the presentation begins with operationalizing Disparity crisis to fight or plight and

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sustainable development. It is of no doubt that the wave of COVID-19 pandemic had posed a serious challenge to all spheres of human life in total manifestation resulting to an avoidable setback which call for an immediate line of action in order to set the wheel rolling. Experiences emanating from the consequences of COVID -19 had shown the wider gap between theories and acquired practical knowledge and skills not only in education but across all discipline. It suffices to state that COVID- 19 pandemic arrival to Nigeria not only created impending challenges but had equally portray gaps and lapses as the impending crises between policy making and Policy implementation (Yakasai, 2021) as well as the deficits in our value system and orientations that have been in existence quite for time immemorial in our school subjects. Yakasai (2021) opined that the present predicament of education should first of all be addressed before thinking of mending the impact covid-19 might have had on its delivery. As concentration on mending the impact will not salvage the decaying education, rather it will decompose it even further.

Conceptualization of Disparity Crises

The concept of disparity crises may mean different things to many particularly to the academic communities and intelligentsia, however depending on one's philosophical orientation and inclination. Disparity crises may be evident when a friction occurs between intent and action, it may equally be explained as an observed gap or lack of congruence between stipulated policies and implementation mechanism. It can also be seen as a discrepancy between theoretical contents of knowledge in a particular discipline or subject area and its practical application towards meeting societal demand. As well as those resulting from human-made disasters and natural afflictions that negatively affect the attainment of national development.

Concept of sustainable development

Sustainable development is a measure or index that explains the possession of adequate national resources, the availability of capital, industrial expertise, technological know-how and an educated labour force for better living standard. Development itself is a process where by a country achieves reasonable self- substantiating qualitative and quantitative improvement which enhances industrial and technological advancement in the interest of its citizens (Kazi, 2012). Some of the pre-requisites for this type of development are; the application of modern science and technology, reasonable political stability, coupled with efficient administration and organization. In a similar vein Wadak (2017) opined that development not only involve economic growth but also conditions in which people in a country have adequate food, security, less poverty, reduced unemployment and income inequality. He maintains that to this point in 1977 “self-reliance “was added to the indices of development. The idea of sustainable development originated from the concept of generative power of how social sciences can influence society. This was coined in 1980 and had been extremely successful in the agenda- setting of international organizations (Ahmad, 2015). It can be discerned from the foregoing that a country can be regarded as a developed nation when the following elements have been achieved:

1. It entails quality and quantity
2. Educated labour force derived from various discipline or sciences
3. Alleviation or total eradication of poverty
4. Reduction in the level of unemployment or total employment for the people
5. Equal distribution of income and
6. The country must be self- reliant. (Garba,2015)

Reflection from the past, present and mirror's the future

It is of no doubt to assert that various subject matters or disciplines either individually or collectively have contributed substantially to Nigeria development. However, the recorded breakthrough of these subject areas cannot be unconnected with embedding the learning process with both theory and practical as well as skill acquisitions in the past prior to the emergence of existing crises which predated the covid 19 pandemic. This is in line with the Nigeria policy document on education which stated that the aims and objectives of education should be directed towards; “ the inculcation of national consciousness and national unity, the right type of values and attitude for the survival of the individual and the Nigerian society, the training of the mind in the understanding of the world around us and the acquisition of appropriate skills, abilities and competence both mental and physical as equipment for the individual to live and contribute to the development of the society. These ratifications were arrived at as a result of the belief that not only is education the greatest force that can be used to bring about redress, it is also the greatest investment that the nation can make for the quick development of the economic, political, sociological and human resources (FGN, 2013)

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A reflection into the past has it on record that teaching of all natural and applied sciences, technology and vocations are complemented by practical experiences which is hoped to be translated into action to meet the scientific and technological aspirations of the society. The same is true for education, arts and literature. For example, 30- 40 years ago, majority of our secondary schools by then were provided with highly equipped and functional laboratories, workshops, as well as farmlands for practical and demonstration purposes. That was the tradition while establishing science colleges, technical and vocational or grammar secondary schools. In this direction teacher training schools were not left behind. The essence, rational and justification of making these provisions are glaringly clear to all, is simply to strike a balance between theoretical knowledge and practical as well as skill acquisition more realistic aimed at achieving desired goals and objectives for national development. Not only that, there is also a close link between schools taught subjects and the realities operating within the immediate environments of the learners in terms of arts and craft. These relations enable learners to appreciate and see relevance of the various school subjects as worthy of study, and also acknowledge their importance for individual self-growth and national development. Putting the claim in other words, a bond of continuity between local crafts such as weaving, leather work, dying, black smith and farming had been firmly rooted in the mind of the learners, of which motivated them intrinsically and extrinsically to strive for perfection, translating into scientific and technological progression. Those are the days in which the child feels excited and elated by virtue of scientific, technological and cultural exhibitions in the forms of young scientists, young engineers, young farmers, young... young in multiple areas. Where are they now? And what happens in the link between theoretical knowledge and practical as well as skill acquisitions? And also, what are the status of laboratories, workshops and school farmlands? Answers to these questions amount to an attempt to resolve one of the crises that pre-dated COVID-19 impetuses to sustainable development

In a parallel dimension one cannot dismiss the link between the various subject matters towards ensuring sustainable development. There is a direct link between agricultural products with either the study of natural and applied sciences, technology or arts and literature. Same consideration goes to the close link between education, science and technology. Furthermore, one cannot separate the connectivity between crafts, science and vocation which stand to be the gateways to sustainable development. For example, agricultural science in all its spheres provide substances for use in pharmacology, which in turn feeds medicine, culminating into healthcare delivery that can be adjudged as an index of development. Equally speaking same agricultural sciences becomes the sole gateway for food production in terms of consumable hydrocarbons, fats and acids, vegetables as well as other mineral resources which are essential for balance diet required to maintain physiological needs of the body to a level of sound equilibration. This impliedly means that a nation capable of feeding itself is regarded as a developed society.

Where people have attained maximum food security there is the likely hood that psychological wellbeing is maximized and can translate into sound labour force. In the same line of argument, a single common source will equally pave way for industrialization by providing raw materials like timber, hide and skin, ground nuts, sesame, kernel nuts and coffee that can be processed or exported for additional economic empowerment and growth of the nation. Same field would become a means for creating job opportunities in multiple ways to absorb the teeming population. This would add another layer of security to the society as all citizens are likely to be engaging in gainful employment, there by closing the room for idleness and unemployment. In essence it's right to assert that the importance of the various subject disciplines as potential means and not an end to sustainable development cannot be underscored. Having seen the extent to which a single vocational subject like agriculture can impact to latitude of a nation's developmental area, with emphasis to food and job security, resources for industrial uses and a feeder to technological and scientific breakthrough. One might ask whether the subject is accorded the status it deserves or not. And why is that the hide and skin derived from animal husbandry which is a unit in the study of agriculture formerly been either locally processed in our local tanneries or exported for economic gain is nowadays been consume to replenish the body instead of healthy meat derived from same common source? Can these drawbacks be attributed to covid 19 pandemic? And if this continues unresolved what would be the future?

Overview of School Subjects Before the Pandemic

A cursory look at the position of arts and literature subjects before the covid 19 pandemic, can reasonably informed us of their contributions to manpower training and human resources for sustainable growth and development prior to the existing disparity crises. These subject areas were believed to be solely responsible for inculcating the right type of attitude and positive value orientations as enshrined in the policy document for education in Nigeria. According to Hogan (1973), as cited in Ononuju, et al. (2013), moral behaviour is determined by five factors as identified below;

1. Socialization; becoming aware as a child of society and parents' rules of conduct for being good

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2. Moral judgement; learning to think reasonably about our own ethics and deliberately deciding on our own moral standards
3. Moral feelings; the internalization of our own moral beliefs to the degree that we fell shame and guilt when we fail to do what we should
4. Empathy; the awareness of other people's situations, feelings and needs so that one is compelled to help those in need
5. Confidence and knowledge; knowing the steps involved in helping others and believing that one is responsible for and capable of helping.

To augment the claims made earlier by Hogan that arts and literature subjects are responsible for training moral values. As subjects of study their relevance in promoting sustainable development squarely stands unique and hinges on the extent to which they are seen as promising means. Hence arts and literature are subjects that train the mind in the matters of moral values. To support this point Mahatma Gandhi of India maintained that;

“If wealth is lost nothing is lost”

“If the health is lost something is lost”

“If character is lost everything is lost”

“Best of all things is character”.

In another vein to buttress the role of these subjects in the inculcation and attainment of moral values, Mkpá (1987) classified values as; spiritual values, family life values, social values, moral values, political values, personal values, economic values as well as scientific and technological values. A holistic attainment of these values will culminate into sustainable development.

Quality Education For Sustainable Development

To vindicate the role of education either as a discipline or as a system in paving the way for sustainable development before the covid 19 pandemic one cannot dismiss the claim that education is an effective weapon whose effect depends on who holds it in his hand and at whom it is aimed. The general concern of education centered on bringing about a desirable and permanent change in the behaviour of the individual. And for this change to occur certain conditions must be met, not only that the change should be evident in manifestation across the cognitive, affective and psycho-motor domains of the individual. Where these changes are made possible, then a valid conclusion and generalization is possible in relation to the attainment of outlined educational objectives enshrined in the policy document on education towards sustainable development. In discussing the relevance of education Obasanjo (2012), outlined what is required of education to become more relevant to our developmental process as,

1. It must train the individual for a better appreciation of his own cultural traditions whilst at the same time equipping him with the ability to absorb new ideas, new information and new data for resolving the constantly changing problems of his environment
2. It must train the individual to relate and interact meaningfully with other individuals in the society and to appreciate the importance of effective organization for human progress
3. It must develop the creative ability of individuals especially in the cultural and technological realms
4. It must foster in the individuals those values which make for good citizenship, such as honesty, selflessness, tolerance, dedication, hard work and personal integrity, all of which provide the rich soil from which good leadership spawned.
5. It must promote the culture of productivity by enabling every individual to discover the creative genius in him.

Obasanjo (2012) further argued that, despite the significant role of education in taking Nigeria to the promising land of sustainable development, yet its quality is declining, this is mainly due to the fact that the quality in some of our schools is deplorable and we now face the specter of ever poorer performance in national examinations. James (2014) lend credence to this point where he express his position that, “ the concern about the quality of education in Nigeria is traceable to the fact that an x-ray of the essential elements of quality of education in Nigeria all shows a deficit in terms of societal participation and ownership of programmes, democratic formulation of policy and adaptability to local conditions, management autonomy, responsive curriculum, qualitative and motivated teaching force, curriculum-driven infrastructure, user friendly materials as well as funding. To catalyze these positions, Enoh (2013) declares that, through the length and breadth of Nigeria, there is overwhelming agreement among both the educated and uneducated that quality at all levels of the system has greatly fallen to unprecedented levels. Most people reflect over the years of educational glory when such and such was the case and find, using different parameters, extreme decline at all levels. In his words Enoh (2013) reiterated that, much of the nations educational problems emanate from underutilization of philosophy of education in training teachers and in decision-making; that the

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policies and decisions which drive, the education system and which to my best understanding have turned it into an educational wasteland are the direct consequences of this neglect.

The positions of Obasanjo (2012), Enoch (2013) and James (2014) are all self-explanatory evidences to the fact that education as a subject matter and a means to sustainable development had greatly suffered from multiple damages in different times which all pre-dated COVID-19 pandemic. These claims also suggested the existing disparities that had plagued the system which inhibit it from enabling Nigeria to reach a level of sustainable development as expected, it is still hazy and the future is becoming a mirage.

Hence, in matters relating to education either as a means or an end product, two principal areas must come to mind for consideration in relation to development, as they ought to be, these are quality and equity. In education quality comes first, but equity is almost of equal importance in the particular context of Nigeria. For one thing education is a universal birth right; for another reason, Nigeria as a state was founded on the democratic promise of ensuring equal opportunity to all citizens, regardless of ethnic, religious, social status or political region. Quality of education depends on several factors most of which have been discussed extensively in many essays, such as curriculum, infrastructure, methods, and environment all have their special value, but quality also depends on teachers, political will and commitment as well as the value system and orientations of the society in addition to the duality of theory and practice. Teachers must be qualified and trained; they should have proper aptitude and commitment. Teachers are not mere conduits of learning; they are viable heroes whom the students would like to admire and emulate. It would therefore, be necessary to make the profession honourable, governmentally as well as socially. And honour would depend not on words but on the personal respect accorded to them in terms of both prestige and financial provision. To qualify this there is an adage that “a poor teacher is not an effective teacher”.

According to Yakasai (2021), long before the advent of corona disease (COVID-19) and the resultant lockdown, the delivery of education in Nigeria was hampered by many pandemics. In fact, the educational system which would have been under state of emergency was characterized by poor academic achievement and other decays in standards. Political will and commitment determine government involvement and investment in education. The UNESCO report on education recommended that at least 26% of the annual budget should be allocated to education at all tiers of government. The claim is amply justified on the simple ground that in our circumstances education is the most productive sector for investment, more than civil administration and military defence. An informed mind would never sell his vote, equally an informed mind hardly compromise standard neither breach the stated rules, nor does he engage in destructive acts. Investment in education would among other things create directly and consequentially employment which is *sine qua non* for economic development.

Another major obstacle that presently hindered quality education is the deliberate separation of experimental or practical knowledge from theoretical knowledge. The teaching of most natural and applied sciences, as well as vocations and education are purely made to become lecture oriented with little or no regard to practical experiences. This changing trend and orientation have grown over the years, peculiarly to save cost and to the inclination of authorities to have graduates over loaded with theoretical content knowledge at the detriment of competent individuals who possess mastery in both theory and standard required for the practices of the various subject matters. Therefore, it is excellently neither right to say, education does not endure nor does it become creative unless given through the blended medium of integrating theory and practice/experiments.

Equity and Quality Issue in Nigerian Education

In Nigeria prior to covid 19 pandemic as quality suffers same goes to equity. The problem of ensuring equity persists, turning from bad to worse. The state is expected to intervene but it does not, because the state itself is metamorphosing into a capitalist society both in ideology and practice. The nation is unequal and polarized, so is across to education. To my believe inequality is destructive, and to employ education in widening the societal gulf instead of bridging it, amount to preparation for anarchy with all its antecedent consequences and underdevelopment. In Nigeria today evidences are bound were the children of the privileged and the elites are opportune to have access to quality education in the somewhat equipped private schools despite their exorbitant cost. Whilst the children of the downtrodden masses who constitute the majority and the electorate whose vote counts, were left with no option rather than the public schools which are ill-equipped, dilapidated, with less or no teaching resources, lack laboratories and in addition to inefficient teachers, who are poorly trained and living in abject / total poverty. Ahmad (2015) contends that social or economic deprivations have its link to government in sensitivity and in-efficacy upon which citizens are dichotomize into “affiliated” and “marginalized”. This is a phenomenon that needs very thorough going into, not only for the sake or interest of education but also that of the wellbeing of the people who are expected to be the potential instruments for sustainable development. Education is a significant human right and the world community has long advocated it for all people in all situations because, education is not only significant as a right, it is also very important in

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enabling people to access other rights and to empower themselves. Obanya, (2002) as cited in Ejue (2014) asserted that, there is need for a shift of emphasis in education discourse from how much and how many to how well. From better and in fact to more of better, this is because the ultimate goal of education is improvement not simply increment.

State of the Art and the Challenges

Over the years a number of policies were formulated and different programmes have been designed by different government of both military and civilian administration with the sole aim of attaining sustainable development. These policies, programme and projects were all directed to enhance quality and quantity in boosting education, agricultural output, scientific and technological mile stones, create job opportunities, improve health delivery and minimize poverty rate among the ever-increasing Nigerian population. Prominent among such government initiated sustainable developmental policies as identified by Margaret & Agnes (2013) include; National Accelerated Food Production Programme (NAFPP) 1972, the Operation Feed the Nation (OFN) 1976; the Green Revolution Programme (GRP) 1980; the Agricultural Development Project (ADP) 1985; The National Directorate of Employment (NDE) 1986; Directorate of Foods, Roads and Rural Infrastructures (DFRRI) 1987; Better life Programme for Rural Women (1987); Family Support Programme (FSP) 1993; the Vision 2020 1996; Family Economic Advancement Programme (FEAP) 1997; Poverty Alleviation Programme (PAP) 2000; National Poverty Eradication Programme (NAPEP) and the Seven (7) Point Agenda (2008). To all these well design and meaningfully enacted policies, one can easily conclude with a heart-felt sorrow that none of them last for more than a decade without been either totally wiped out or silently extinguished. Another similitude to the extinction of laudable project is the deplorable condition of the Nigerians giant and multi-purpose steel rolling mills located at Ajaokuta, to which trillions of naira had yearly been injected into it from inception to date. Shamefully the iron company is left abandoned unproductive/underutilize despite the substantial iron deposit in the country. Similar example could be cited with reference to the Nigerian oil and gas sector, even though the country is among the world's major exporter of crude oil, yet our refineries' hardly produce the required PSM for internal or domestic consumption.

This discussion would not be comprehensive if we fail to admit that as the world is moving from dependence in hydroelectric power supply to tapping and combating sunlight to solar energy, yet the net megawatt supply of energy in Nigeria is far below the required. Going by the available fertile landmass, natural flowing rivers, and abundant deposits of crude oil, iron ores, and other mineral resources, variant vegetation zones coupled with higher human resources, the effects of all these are hardly noted in sustaining development as expected. These poor trends in the identified sectors have impeded sustainable development in the country not because of the inefficiency of the various subjects of study in our school systems, neither to the multiplier effect of covid -19.

From the foregoing discourse it appears that sustainable development in Nigeria had been in either emergency or crises state which pre-dated COVID-19 pandemic. Both loud and silent emergencies have pervaded the possible avenues for development to strive. Loud emergencies that include human made disasters (like civil strife in forms of communal crises, banditry, kidnapping abduction and misplacement of priorities) and natural disasters (like, earthquakes, floods and pandemics) and silent emergencies that include HIV/AIDS, extreme poverty, children living in streets, (Pigozzi, 1999), compromising standard and poor value system and orientation in addition to lack of political will and commitments to policy implementation. Uemura (1999) asserted that, Emergency often result in situations where formal education system might be destroyed or damaged, teachers, education staff and students might be killed, abducted, injured or unable to resume normal school operations.

As noted, crises or emergency conditions differs in magnitude, directions and manifestations, this is also true to state that, while emergencies or crises created by a disaster may relatively last for a short term, crises or emergencies created by on-going conflicts, war or poor policy implementation, and value orientation may last for years if not decades. Yakasai (2021) have identified almost nine (9) major challenges or crises facing the Nigerian education sector as follows.

1. Poor academic performance
2. Poor governance and management of education
3. Poor funding and neglect of the education sector
4. Poor infrastructure and teaching facilities
5. Overcrowded classrooms/lecture rooms
6. Poor teachers welfare
7. Lack of dedication and commitment to work by teachers
8. Changes in learners value orientations

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9. Influence of media technology
10. High rate of examination malpractice

These crises were all due to human made disasters that has a direct implications or impact to the teaching and learning of the various school subjects. They constitute a cog to the attainment of the nation's dream for sustainable development. These claims lend credence to view of Pigozzi, (1999), that loud and silent emergencies have pervaded the possible avenues for development to strive. Loud emergencies that include human made disasters (like civil strife in forms of communal crises, banditry, political bigotry, inefficiency greed and egocentrism) and natural disasters (like, earthquakes, floods and pandemics) and silent emergencies that include HIV/AIDS, extreme poverty, children living in streets,

In Nigeria today a number of school age children are roaming the streets, some are living in extreme poverty with many facing difficulties to have three square meals in a day, our systems are negatively affected by constant policy changes with none having withstood the test of time, and education system lacks the glory of duality between theory and practice. The aforementioned situation had resulted into putting Nigeria into an emergency position to which Sinclair, (2002) claimed its education should be "that which protects the wellbeing, foster learning opportunities and nurtures the overall development of children affected by conflicts and disasters. Nicolai (2003) further suggested that education should be seen as a priority component of emergency assistance as it lays an important role in meeting children's basic needs in both the short and long terms and help to reduce vulnerability to disaster. To this point Bensalah (2002) stated (5) five reasons why educational response in emergencies and reconstruction might be required;

1. Education helps meet the psychological needs of the children
2. It's a tool for protecting children in emergencies
3. It provides a channel for conveying health and survival messages for teaching new skills and values
4. It's a tool for social cohesion
5. Education is vital to the reconstruction of economic basis of the family and the larger society

Factors of Low level of Development in Nigeria

The low level of development in Nigeria may have its root from the following factors that have been lingering in its neck.

1. Disparity between policy and implementation mechanisms; despite the fact that successive government have evolved meaningful policies and projects geared towards sustainable development. Yet majority of these policies were left either half-baked or totally ignored before attaining their full maturation stage. These need immediate redress by government officials and those in positions of authority and mantle of power. Nigeria as a developing nation has substantial manpower that is blessed with the capacity to formulate policies required for any desired development.
2. Disparity in value system and orientation; there exist a wider gap between what is enshrined in our civic curriculum in terms of what constitute value systems and orientation and our attitude in real life situations. The disparity in value systems need to be re-evaluated by all to be in line with positive value system and orientations as suggested by Obasanjo, (2012). In essence a positive change is required, which is consonant with the ontological, epistemological as well as methodological concerns of what value system and orientation stands for.
3. Poor political will and commitment; noting that policies are only enacted by government, and it has been a tradition that each government comes up with its own policies, so doing should not negate the principle of continuity. Laudable policies ought to be considered whenever there is a change in government. Equivocally continuity of meaningful developmental projects emanating from sound and well-articulated policies would add vigour and taste to our claim for democratic dispensation or popular democracy
4. Compromising standard; in pursuance of sustainable development compromising standard need to be detested and shun off. Evidences are bound where standards have been compromised. For example, most recently built classrooms have become dilapidated, roads of nowadays hardly withstand pressure from loaded trucks whilst many of the commodities both consumable and non-consumables are either substandard or of low quality. Similarly standard at times are compromise in the selection and recruitment of teachers at various levels of our education system. These practices do have negative multiplier consequences on the students, parents, the system and the larger society. Where adequate preparations are made in terms of input there is a higher expectation of output. Hence reciprocal equity in education stem from the quality of the teachers.
5. Neglects of local trade and crafts; there is a need for a serious concern to reintegrate the local trades and crafts simultaneously with the school subjects. This is because of the immense role and significance in promoting mastery of vocational subjects taught in schools. Incorporating /integrating trades like metal works, dying, knitting, weaving, will

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inevitably arose learners curiosity and motivation to related school subjects, in similar vein traditional medicine/ and herbal processing should also be given value in the teaching of science.

6. Appreciating the genius and creative inventions of our younger ones; As each individual is bestowed with latent potentialities which are only made known apparently through exhibition, if our scientific and technological quest for advancement is to become a reality, it then becomes necessary to appreciate our indigenous creative inventions and at the same time support them in all respect to boost their morale to continue with exploring their God given talents and abilities.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it suffices to reiterate my position by saying again that covid 19 pandemic has only exposes the shortfalls and weakness in Nigeria not by virtue of low or poor curriculum content of the school subjects. But rather due to the deficits that have been orchestrated by poor policy implementation, deliberate segregation of theory from practice and experiments coupled with poor and insensitive value systems orientations and compromising standards. These are disparity gaps need to be filled in holistically as they exemplified emergencies worthy to attend. The present predicament of under development in Nigeria should be seen from these lenses with reasonable attempt to address them before thinking of the impact covid-19 might have had on the school subject matters and their relations to sustainable development. As concentration on mending the Impact will not salvage the decay and rot in our quest for sustainable development, rather it will decompose it even further leaving the nation in a state of deepened crises to fight or flight.

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